

SOCIAL AND ETHICAL VIEWS OF THE SCHOLARS OF SUFISM IN THE EDUCATION OF A PERFECT HUMAN BEING

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***Annotatsiya:** In this article, based on the main pillars and ideas of Islam, new social-political, spiritual-ethical thoughts and ideas were put forward in Sufism, and the concepts of the meaning of life, human value, divine love, justice, humanity, and perfection were further developed. It is stated that it has been scientifically determined.*

***Key words:** Sufism, perfect man, morality, education, science, education, sustainable development.*

СОЦИАЛЬНО-ЭТИЧЕСКИЕ УСТАНОВКИ СУФИСТОВ В ВОСПИТАНИИ СОВЕРШЕННОГО ЧЕЛОВЕКА

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***Аннотация:** В данной статье на основе основных столпов и идей ислама выдвигаются новые общественно-политические, духовно-этические мысли и идеи в суфизме, а также концепции смысла жизни, человеческой ценности, божественной любви, справедливости, гуманности, и совершенство получили дальнейшее развитие. Утверждается, что это было научно определено.*

***Ключевые слова:** Суфизм, совершенный человек, мораль, образование, наука, образование, устойчивое развитие.*

KOMIL INSON TARBIYASIDA TASAVVUF ALLOMALARINING IJTIMOIY-AXLOQIY QARASHLARI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada Tasavvuf ta'limotida islomning asosiy arkonlari, g'oyalariga tayangan holda, yangi ijtimoiy-siyosiy, ma'naviy-axloqiy fikrlar, g'oyalar ilgari surildi va hayot mazmuni, inson qadri, ilohiy sevgi, adolat, insoniylik, komillik tushunchalari yanada ilmiy aniqlashtirilganligi bayon qilingan.

Tayanch so'zlar: Tasavvuf, komil inson, axloq, ta'lim, fan, tarbiya, barqaror taraqqiyot.

It is known from the history of our nation that Sufism and its sects occupy a great place in the development of national spirituality and ideology. "Sufism has acquired a very important importance in the social life of Central Asian peoples and groups of social categories, and in particular in their spiritual and educational development," writes the well-known scientist B. Valikhojhaev. In fact, the philosophical, religious, artistic works, ideas and views of the sheikhs of Kubraviya, Yassaviya, Naqshbandiya and other sects of Sufism have been serving in the development of the spirituality and morality of the worldview of our people.

Sufism sheikhs thought about the problems of human life and dreamed about their social ideal and what a just society would be like. In their perfected ideal of a just society, the principles of human dignity, equality of all before God, human will and freedom occupy the main place. In the work of the sheikhs of the Naqshbandi sect, religious tolerance, goodwill towards representatives of other religions, and the idea and thoughts of brotherhood of different peoples and peoples prevail. Sufism sheikhs analyzed and interpreted social, economic, political processes and events and

put forward valuable socio-political and educational ideas. They glorify the work and lifestyle of workers, especially artisans and peasants.

It should be noted that Naqshbandi sheikhs promoted the ideals of a perfect human being and a just society, and showed that a person should always live with hope and aspiration and fight to achieve his goal. When thinking about the social and spiritual ideal in Sufism, it should also be noted that Sufists, as ideologues of their time, believed that inequalities in the social and economic spheres and differences in personal abilities and talents were caused primarily by God and by the laziness and sinfulness of people. First of all, they failed to deeply analyze the objective factors and ways of establishing social equality, freedom, social conditions and justice for individual freedom and rights. Sufism sheikhs, at the same time, came up with innovative ideas and thoughts about improving social life and establishing justice even at that time. In this regard, their opinions about the need for a person to live knowing himself and the world, to live with an understanding of socio-political and moral problems are particularly noteworthy.

Socio-political and moral ideals of Sufism sheikhs were definitely formed on the basis of demands and needs, main problems of the social life of that time. Conflicts, feudal disunity, oppression and injustice in the social and political life of the Middle Ages East were expressed in the teachings of Sufism. The basis of commonality and diversity in the views, ideas, and ideals of Sufism sheikhs lies in the economic-political, social, and spiritual reality of the regions and countries where they lived. Sufism's advanced thoughts and ideas, efforts to establish justice, peace, and stability in society are a requirement of events and conflicts in social life. In Iran, Khorasan, and Movarounnahr, some Sufi sects were formed against the official political power, as the spirituality and official ideology of the opposition forces, and even served it.

Based on the main pillars and ideas of Islam, new social-political, spiritual-ethical thoughts and ideas were put forward in Sufism, and the concepts of the meaning of life, human value, divine love, justice, humanity, and perfection were

scientifically clarified. For example, Hazrat Bahauddin Naqshband's "The requirement of the goal, that is, no matter how diligent you are in the path of acquiring knowledge and reaching the Truth, I will never forgive you if you step on my head and pass it». An example of this is his call. The mystics, who studied the life of peoples, peoples, groups, categories, from country to country, called the representatives of different nationalities and religions to solidarity, cooperation and tolerance. As the people of their time, they created their social and moral ideals about the society and the state where social justice was established. They observed a stable, prosperous society in which human dignity, free will, rights and well-being are ensured. The sheikhs of Sufism understood the ideal society and state, a theocratic state based on the principles of Sharia, with the ideology of Sufism as a priority. Of course, they also put forward the idea of electing the tsar. Contrary to the views of official Islamic scholars, they emphasized the need to use history, jurisprudence and other worldly sciences in the management of the state, and they themselves developed valuable new ideas in this regard. In particular, the sheikhs of Malomatia, Naqshbandia, Kubravia, and Sukhrovardia sects emphasize that science is light and that a person cannot live without religious and worldly knowledge. Although Sufism schools and sects differ from each other in terms of some laws, rituals, formal signs, methods (jahriya, secret, external, internal), they have commonality and integrity in terms of essence, content, main goals and requirements.

It is known from the history of the peoples of Iran, Khurasan and Movarunnahr that superstition, ignorance, and ignorance have brought great calamities and tragedies to the world. Sufists who well understood the true nature and importance of religion fought against ignorance as people of knowledge, actively participated in solving socio-political and spiritual problems in certain historical situations, followed the people and various categories, and helped them in the society. those of great standing. The representatives of Sufism with great courage and courage opposed the existing evils in the society, the selfishness and selfishness of the ruling circles. The works and life activities of Abdullah Ansari, Ardasher Abbadi, Makhdumi Azam,

Khoja Ahrori Vali can be a confirmation of our opinion. According to them, in a just society, conditions should be created for the cooperation and integrity of groups and peoples, as well as human dignity and value, and for spiritual growth.

The sheikhs of the Naqshbandi sect interpret that the state is created by the will of Allah as the only form of human existence to manage affairs, relationships and maintain order on earth, without the state there will be no human society. According to Sheikh Makhdumi A'zam, the rulers should manage the state without retreating from religious and secular laws, and work by combining religious, political and legal tasks. In his opinion, because the kings did not know and violated the sharia, mystics are obliged to interfere in the work of state administration.

"In order to reduce violence and "reduce the hand of evil", it is necessary for sheikhs to intervene in politics and communicate with sultans".

In today's world, when ideological struggles have intensified, learning the teachings of Sufism is of great importance in determining the true essence of holy Islam and forming a perfect person. This teaching is very useful in exposing the people of fanatics and terrorists who use religion as a mask and threaten peace and stability with subversiveness and destruction. Our people, who are building a legal, democratic and civil society, will certainly achieve a prosperous, free and prosperous life by critically using the spiritual heritage, historical experience and values of Islam and Sufism. Because our great grandfathers left a rich legacy by developing moral rules and norms about how a person behaves in a family, community, wedding, maraka, conversation, in short, in various situations. Their way of life and way of life is an example for us.

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